

Constitution of the Active Principle of *Chita*. Part I.

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Chitraka or *Chita* as it is more commonly known in Bengal and the United Provinces is the root of a plant which grows throughout the year as cultivated or wild shrubs under three distinct botanical classifications: (1) *Plumbago rosea*, (2) *Plumbago zeylanica* and (3) *Plumbago europoea*. *P. rosea* is very common in Bengal whereas *P. zeylanica* is more generally met with in the U. P. *P. europoea* is comparatively rare in both the provinces principally because of the fact that being a comparatively more delicate plant it can only exist under cultivated conditions. *Chita* has been quite well known in our country from a very long time, and there are references to it in the classical works of Charaka, Susruta and Muhammad Husian. Therein its vesicant, stimulative, acrid and antiseptic properties are widely made use of in various prescriptions for dyspepsia, paralysis, rheumatism, cough, leprosy, plague and a host of other diseases. The caustic properties of *Chita* have also found illegal applications in causing abortions and poisoning, numerous cases of which have been recorded in the various works on Indian medical jurisprudence.

The active principle of *Chita* or 'plumbagin,' as has been named by the author, was first isolated by Dulong in 1885 (*Pharmacographica Indica*, Vol II, p. 332) by extracting the roots of *P. europoea* with ether and obtained in the form of shining yellow needles by crystallisation from alcohol. Later on Fluckiger in 1887 isolated the same substance in a slightly purer form from the roots of *P. zeylanica* by submitting them to steam distillation and extracting the distillate with ether. In 1888 Bettinck (*Haarlems Tijdsch*, Jan., 1888) also isolated plumbagin from *P. rosea* in the form of yellow needles from hot water melting at 72°, and he was of the opinion that the composition of the substance was best represented by the formula $C_6H_{13}O_6$.

After these preliminary investigations dating back to more than forty years, there has not been any further publications about the constitution of *Chita*, and the following investigation was undertaken regarding the constitution of the substance which is decidedly of great physiological importance.

Plumbagin is present in all the three varieties of plants to a maximum of about 0.9-1 per cent. *P. rosea* and *P. zeylanica* contain approximately the same proportion of plumbagin whereas *P. europaea* contains much less. The exact proportion of plumbagin in these plants varies within wide limits according to the locality, growth, age, condition of the soil, season of the year and many other considerations. In general it is found that the bigger the plant and the drier the soil, the greater is the quantity of plumbagin found in the roots. It has also been found that fresh roots yield a much greater proportion of plumbagin than roots which have been stored for a considerable time. That is the reason why bazaar Chita yields comparatively so little of plumbagin. It is just possible that the plumbagin in the roots are destroyed to a considerable extent on long storage due to oxidation.

For extracting plumbagin the best solvent that has yet been found is petroleum ether (b. p. 70°-90°), and the substance is best crystallised from dilute alcohol. The melting point (78°) of plumbagin as isolated by the present authors is 6° higher than that obtained by Bettinck, which probably indicates a much purer specimen. The analytical data together with the molecular weight determined by the cryoscopic method in benzene point to the conclusion that plumbagin must be represented by the molecular formula $C_{18}H_{14}O_5$. On oxidation by neutral or alkaline potassium permanganate in the cold plumbagin yields benzoic and cinnamic acids, whereas by distillation with zinc dust it produces naphthalene and β -methyl-naphthalene. These facts together with the yellow colour and the penetrating quinone like smell of plumbagin make one liable to think that plumbagin might be a derivative of *p*-benzoquinone or α -naphthoquinone. This conclusion is also supported by the fact that plumbagin in acetic acid solution is very easily reduced by zinc dust to a colourless leuco compound, which is oxidised by atmospheric air back to yellow plumbagin with the greatest rapidity. Further confirmation of its quinone structure is obtained by the fact that though by the action of hydroxylamine plumbagin yields a dioxime, yet phenylhydrazine and semicarbazide produce only mono-phenylhydrazone and mono-semicarbazone respectively, just in the same way as α -naphthoquinone. By the action of fuming nitric acid plumbagin yields a tetranitro derivative. Bromine in alcohol, chloroform or carbon tetrachloride solution very readily acts on plumbagin forming a dibromo addition product, which points to the unsaturated character of the former.

Plumbagin is a neutral substance. By the action of aqueous or alcoholic ferric chloride it develops a red colour and it dissolves to a cherry-red solution in alkalis. It also gives a dirty green precipitate with alcoholic copper acetate. From these it might be presumed that plumbagin contains one or more phenolic hydroxy groups. This is supported by the fact that by the action of acetyl chloride, benzoyl chloride and ethyl chlorocarbonate, plumbagin in pyridine solution yields the corresponding monoacetyl, mono-benzoyl and monocarbethoxy derivatives respectively.

Thus of the five atoms of oxygen present in the plumbagin molecule, three are easily accounted for, namely two in a paraquinone grouping and one in a phenolic hydroxy group. In absence of any methoxy groups, the remaining two oxygen atoms are most probably in a lactone grouping. This assumption is based on the fact that plumbagin has some of the properties of an aromatic lactone like coumarin. Like the latter, an alkaline solution of plumbagin also precipitates a different compound on acidification which gradually reverts to the original plumbagin on standing in contact with mineral acids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Isolation of Plumbagin.—Air dried roots of *P. rosea* or *seylanica* are cut to bits of about 5 mm. in length by means of a chopping machine, and then they are exhaustively extracted by means of petroleum ether (b. p. 70°-90°) in a large Soxhlet extractor preferably made of metal. The dark orange-yellow solution on distillation to a small volume and allowing to stand for some time exposed to the air, deposits the crude plumbagin in the form of fine glistening needles of a golden yellow colour. They are then recrystallised several times from dilute alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal, and finally obtained in the form of beautiful silky needles, m. p. 77-78°. (Found: C, 69.1, 68.96; H, 4.8, 4.8; M. W. = 296 (cryoscopic in benzene). $C_{15}H_{10}O_2$ requires C, 69.4; H, 4.8 per cent. M. W. = 311).

The substance is very soluble in ether, chloroform, acetone, benzene, acetic acid, etc., moderately soluble in hot water and almost insoluble in cold water. It volatilises with steam, and can be sublimed without decomposition on careful heating. It gives a blood-red colour with ferric chloride and a dirty green precipitate

with alcoholic copper acetate. Silver nitrate, lead acetate or calcium chloride does not give any precipitate. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish brown colour which changes to violet on warming. It dissolves in caustic alkalis and ammonia with a cherry-red colour at first, but this gradually changes to a reddish brown shade on standing in contact with air probably due to oxidation or hydrolysis. The cherry-red solution on acidification gives a precipitate of the original substance, but the reddish brown solution on similar treatment gives an altogether different product. The substance whether in the solid state or in solution produces blisters very easily in contact with the skin, and even very dilute solutions produce a black stain. The substance reduces Fehling's solution, but not ammoniacal silver nitrate.

Monoacetyl plumbagin, $C_{18}H_{14}O_5 \cdot C_2H_3O$.

Two gms. of plumbagin were dissolved in 10 c.c. of pyridine and 5 c.c. of acetyl chloride gradually added. After the vigorous reaction had subsided the mixture was warmed on the water-bath for a short time and then poured into water. The resulting crystalline brown precipitate was filtered off and recrystallised from dilute alcohol in brownish yellow needles melting at 138° . (Found: C, 67.7; H, 5.5. $C_{20}H_{17}O_6$ requires C, 67.9; H, 5.09 per cent.).

Monobenzyl plumbagin, $C_{18}H_{14}O_5 \cdot C_7H_5O$.

This was prepared by the action of benzoyl chloride on plumbagin in pyridine solution in a manner exactly similar to the above. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow prisms melting at 147° . (Found: C, 71.9; H, 4.9. $C_{25}H_{19}O_6$ requires C, 72.2; H, 4.5 per cent.).

Monocarbethoxy plumbagin, $C_{18}H_{14}O_5 \cdot C_3H_5O_2$.

This was prepared from plumbagin and ethyl chlorocarbonate in a manner similar to the above. It crystallised from dilute alcohol in yellowish brown needles melting at 109° . (Found: C, 65.3; H, 5.3. $C_{21}H_{16}O_7$ requires C, 65.7; H, 4.9 per cent.).

Plumbagin-dioxime, $C_{18}H_{14}O_5 : (NOH)_2$.

Two gms. of plumbagin dissolved in 15 c.c. of pyridine were treated with 3 gms. of hydroxylamine hydrochloride and the mixture heated on the water-bath for about half an hour. It was then

poured into water and the resulting crystalline yellow precipitate recrystallised from alcohol in bright yellow needles melting at 220°. It dissolves in sodium hydroxide with a yellow-brown colour. (Found: N, 7.9. $C_{18}H_{17}O_5N_3$ requires N, 8.2 per cent.).

Plumbagin monophenylhydrazone, $C_{18}H_{15}O_4$: $N.NH.C_6H_5$.

Two gms. of plumbagin dissolved in 20 c.c. of glacial acetic acid were treated with 3 gms. of phenylhydrazine dissolved in 10 c.c. of the same solvent. The mixture was heated on the water-bath for about an hour and then poured into water. The viscous precipitate was filtered off and crystallised from alcohol with the addition of animal charcoal in fine reddish brown needles melting at 198°. It gives a violet colour with concentrated sulphuric acid and dissolves in organic solvents with a reddish brown colour. (Found: N, 6.5. $C_{22}H_{21}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.9 per cent.).

Plumbagin monosemicarbazone, $C_{18}H_{15}O_4$: $N.NH.CO.NH_2$.

This was prepared from plumbagin and semicarbazide hydrochloride in a manner similar to the dioxime. It crystallises from a mixture of pyridine and alcohol in light brown needles melting above 280°. (Found: N, 11.1. $C_{18}H_{15}O_5N_3$ requires N, 11.4 per cent.).

Action of Potassium Permanganate on Plumbagin.

Five gms. of plumbagin dissolved in dilute sodium hydroxide were treated with a 3% solution of potassium permanganate in the cold until the latter was no longer decolorised. The precipitated manganese dioxide was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to a small volume after neutralization with dilute hydrochloric acid. It was then rendered strongly acid with hydrochloric acid when a colourless crystalline precipitate was obtained. The latter melted at 132°, and was identified to be cinnamic acid. The mother-liquor on extraction with ether yielded a further small quantity of cinnamic acid together with traces of benzoic and acetic acids. No other product could be detected.

Action of Fuming Nitric Acid.

Five gms. of plumbagin were treated with 25 c.c. of fuming nitric acid in the cold. The substance rapidly dissolved with slight rise of temperature, but no nitrous fumes were evolved. The

mixture was warmed on the water-bath for a short time and then poured into water. The bright yellow precipitate thus obtained was crystallised from alcohol in fine needles melting at 172° , and was found to be a tetranitro derivative. (Found: N, 10.9. $C_{10}H_4O_8(NO_2)_4$ requires N, 11.4 per cent.)

Action of Bromine.—Plumbagin dissolved in alcohol was treated with successive small quantities of bromine and the solution warmed on the water-bath until the bromine was no longer decolorised. The solution was poured into water and the resultant product crystallised from alcohol in bright yellow needles melting at 122° . It was found to be plumbagin dibromide. (Found: Br, 34.4. $C_{10}H_2O_8Br_2$ requires Br, 33.9 per cent.)

Distillation with Zinc Dust.—Five gms. of plumbagin were distilled with zinc dust in a current of hydrogen in the manner already described (this *Journal*, 1928, 4, 28). The distillate which contained both a crystalline substance and a liquid, smelt very strongly of naphthalene. The liquid gave a picrate with picric acid melting at 112° , and was identified to be β -methyl-naphthalene. There was also a small quantity of a brownish tarry substance from which nothing definite could be isolated or identified.

Further work in this direction is in progress.

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